

HANDS-ON HIGH-FIDELITY WEB ARCHIVING WITH BROWSERTRIX

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Abstract – The workshop will provide participants an opportunity to learn about the practice of web archiving through a hands-on, guided session where attendees will have a chance to create their own web archives using browser-based open source tooling (Browsertrix), and then discuss the experience with creators of the tools and experienced practitioners in the field.

Submission Type – Workshop.

Keywords – Web Archive Content, Open Source Software, Training, Browsertrix, Webrecorder.

Conference Topics – Haerenga – Journey

I. INTRODUCTION

Browsertrix is an open-source browser-based web archiving system designed to allow anyone to archive complex, interactive websites as accurately as possible. Browsertrix uses real web browsers to crawl web pages, allowing for customizations of crawling process, as well as a presentation and curation layer for publicly sharing archived collections.

In this workshop, we will cover the basic workflow of web archiving with Browsertrix, including identifying the scope and requirements for a crawl, starting and running the crawl, checking quality via replay, and sharing and curation. The workshop most closely relates to the theme of Harenga, as web archiving is a continuing and evolving journey!

To participate in the hands-on portion of the workshop, attendees should bring their own laptop. No additional software is required beyond a modern

web browser. The web crawling will be done in the cloud using a hosted version of Browsertrix running the latest version of the software.

Depending on the interest of participants, we will also cover more advanced topics such as customizable behaviors, large scale crawling, patching crawls, social media, and quality assurance tools.

We will also present the experience of the National Library of New Zealand, who have been using Browsertrix for several years, about the successes and unique challenges that they have faced in using Browsertrix from the perspective of a library doing national-scale web archiving. Participants will be able to share their experience, what worked and what didn't, during the interactive session. We will also discuss the shared challenges ahead and future / ongoing work on Browsertrix.

II. WORKSHOP STRUCTURE

The workshop will be structured as follows:

30 min - Introduction to Web Archiving and Browsertrix Demo

60 min - Hands-on crawling and curation with the Browsertrix application.

30 min - Discussion with developers, NLNZ and other existing users.

III. GOALS

The workshop will be beneficial to participants of all levels. Newcomers to web archiving will learn the basics of web archiving with Browsertrix. Existing users / advanced practitioners will gain new insights about the very latest developments in the open source Browsertrix software (including brand new features designed to deal with larger scale crawling) and will get a chance to discuss the ongoing challenges in high-fidelity web archiving with both developers and experienced users of the software. Participants will be able to leave with a better understanding of web archiving, and if they choose, their very own web archive that they can download from Browsertrix and self-host.

AUTHOR BIOGRAPHIES

Ilya Kreymer - Lead Developer and Creator of the Webrecorder project. Ilya has been developing various open source web archiving tools under the Webrecorder umbrella since 2014.

Gillian Lee - Coordinator, Web Archives at the National Library of New Zealand. Gillian has been involved in building the Library's web collections since 2007.

